

less cubes of apigenin triacetate (4a-acetate) (35 mg), m.p. 182°, mol. wt. 396 (M).

Kayaflavone (1d): CLV (50 mg) was acetylated with Ac₂O and pyridine and the product was crystallised from CHCl₃-MeOH to give colourless cubes of kayaflavone triacetate (1d-acetate) (30 mg), m.p. 190-192°, mol. wt. 706 (M).

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Triterpenoids and Flavonoids from the

Leaves of *Pongamia glabra* Vent.

Demethylation Studies on 5-Methoxyfuranoflavones

BANI TALAPATRA*, ASOK K. MALLIK**
and

SUNIL K. TALAPATRA*

Department of Chemistry, University College of Science,
University of Calcutta, Calcutta-700 009

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PONGAMIA glabra Vent. (Fam. Leguminosae) is well-known for producing furano-, pyrano- and simple flavonoids¹. Our recent investigation^{1,2} on the flowers of this plant led to the isolation of a number

** Present Address: Department of Chemistry, Jadavpur University, Calcutta-700 032.

of flavonoids along with two triterpenoids, cycloart-23-ene-3 β , 25-diol and friedelin, and one phenylalanine derived dipeptide aurantiamide acetate. No triterpenoid or dipeptide was previously isolated from this plant although Mahey *et al.*³ reported the possibility of occurrence of terpenoids in the leaves. The leaves of *P. glabra* were, therefore, reinvestigated particularly with a view to study their non-flavonoid constituents.

In this reinvestigation, four triterpenoids, cycloart-23-ene-3 β , 25-diol, friedelin, lupeol and lupenone, four furanoflavones, karanjin, 5-methoxyfuran(4'',5''-8,7)flavone (1), pongapin and 3'-methoxypongapin, one chromenoflavone pongachromene, one simple flavone kanugin, and β -sitosterol have been isolated. Pongapin (m.p. 190°), 3'-methoxypongapin (m.p. 182°), and pongachromene (m.p. 195°) have been characterised from their uv, ir and ¹H nmr spectral features and the other compounds by direct comparison with the authentic samples^{1,3,4}.

Dried and powdered leaves (1 kg) of *P. glabra* were extracted in a Soxhlet apparatus with chloroform for 40 h. The concentrate of the extract (38 g) was chromatographed over silica gel, elution being carried out with solvents and solvent mixtures of increasing polarities. The results are presented in Table 1.

TABLE-1

Eluent	Compound isolated	Amount mg
Light petrol-EtOAc		
97:3	Lupenone	16
97:3	Friedelin	10
95:5	Lupeol	106
9:1	β -Sitosterol	210
9:1	Karanjin	182
85:15	Pongapin	10
85:15	Pongachromene	22
4:1	3'-Methoxypongapin	18
4:1	Kanugin	108
4:1	Cycloart-23-ene-3 β , 25-diol	4
2:1	5-Methoxyfuran(4'',5''-8,7)flavone (1)	82

In our earlier papers we reported^{1,5} that the ¹H and ¹³C nmr signals for the OCH₃ group of 5-methoxyfuran(4'',5''-8,7)flavone (1) appeared at higher fields than those of its linear isomer pinnatin (2). The ¹H nmr signal for the chelated OH of pongaglabol (3) also appeared¹ at a higher field than that of 5-hydroxyfuran(4'',5''-6,7)flavone (4). These differences were thought to be due to the different mode of fusion of the furano moiety to the flavone nucleus (8,7 in 1 and 3 and 6,7 in 2 and 4) effecting different extent of electron transfer from the C-5 OCH₃ or OH to the flavone carbonyl site. Here we report the observed differences in demethylation of the 5-methoxyfuranoflavones, 1 and 2, under mild demethylating conditions, (i) refluxing with 6 N ethanolic HCl⁶ and (ii) treatment with dry AlCl₃ at room temperature⁷, generally

applied for selective demethylation of the 5-OCH₃ group of flavones.

On refluxing with 6 *N* ethanolic HCl for 10 h, **2** underwent complete demethylation producing **4**, while under identical condition **1** was only slightly (~5%) demethylated. When an ethereal solution of **2** was treated with dry AlCl₃, it was completely demethylated within 48 h¹, but under the same condition **1** remained mainly (~90%) unconverted. On increasing the time of the AlCl₃-induced reaction to 7 days, **1** was found to undergo about 30% demethylation. This difference in the reactivities of **1** and **2** may also be ascribed to their difference in the sites of fusion of the furano moiety to the flavone nucleus.

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Chemical Investigation of the Aerial Parts of Different *Clerodendron* Species

KRISHNA C. JOSHI*, P. SINGH and RAVINDRA K. SINGH

Department of Chemistry, University of Rajasthan,
Jaipur-302 004

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IN pursuing our interest¹ in terpenoid constituents of the *Clerodendron* genus (Verbenaceae), we have examined *Clerodendron splendens* Don., an ornamental climbing shrub having red flowers, and *Cleroden-*

dron neutens Wall., a bushy shrub. The plants were collected from the Taj Garden, Agra, and carefully identified by the Horticulture Department. A perusal of literature reveal that no work has been reported on any part of *Clerodendron splendens* and *Clerodendron neutens*. Chemical investigation of their aerial parts was, therefore, undertaken and the results are summarised in this communication.

The light-petroleum extract of the aerial parts of the *C. splendens* afforded Clerodolone, (24s)ethylcholesta-5,22,25-triene-3 β -ol, n-triacontane, friedelan-3 β -ol, friedelan-3-one and β -amyrin; while clerosterol, clerodolone, (24s)ethylcholesta-5,22,25-triene-3 β -ol, β -sitosterol and stigmasterol have been isolated from the light-petroleum extract of the *C. neutens*.

Experimental

Completely air-dried and coarsely powdered aerial parts of *C. splendens* (3.0 kg) and *C. neutens* (3.0 kg) were repeatedly extracted with light-petroleum (b.p. 60-80) on steam-bath for 3 \times 12 h separately. The extracts were concentrated under reduced pressure and the resulting brownish mass was chromatographed over 60-120 mesh silica-gel (350 g) using a borosil glass column of size 3' \times 2.5" separately.

Chromatographic fractions were collected in the following order in *C. splendens*: Fraction 1 (petrol), Fraction 2 (petrol-C₆H₆, 1:1), Fraction 3 (C₆H₆), Fraction 4 (C₆H₆-CH₃COOC₂H₅, 9:1), Fraction 5 (C₆H₆-CH₃COOC₂H₅, 1:1), Fraction 6 (CH₃-COOC₂H₅) and Fraction 7 (CH₃COOC₂H₅-MeOH, 9:1). Purity of each fraction was checked on tlc plate (silica-gel) using various solvent mixtures as eluents and the following compounds were obtained in pure state after repeated crystallisation. The identity of the compounds were confirmed by spectral (ir, ¹H nmr, mass) and chemical studies as well as by co-tlc with authentic samples. The spots on tlc plates were visualised using 1% ceric sulphate in 2 *N* H₂SO₄ as spray reagent.

(24s)Ethylcholesta-5,22,25-triene-3 β -ol: Yellowish white solid (100 mg) was obtained after removal of the solvent from light-petrol and benzene (1:1) fraction. Crystallisation from light petrol gave colourless needles, m.p. 144-45°; ν_{\max} (nujol) 3450-3230 (OH), 1640 and 800 cm⁻¹; δ (CDCl₃) 0.7 (3H, s), 0.95 (3H, s), 1.00 (3H, d), 1.65 (3H, brs), 0.83 (3H, t), 4.68 (1H, dd), 3.5 (1H, m), 5.22 (1H, dd), 5.3 (2H, m), *M*⁺, 410, C₂₉H₄₆O; acetate (Ac₂O/Py), m.p. 140°^a.

Friedelan-3-one: Benzene fraction on repeated crystallisation gave colourless needles (150 mg), m.p. 258-59°; gave positive Liebermann-Burchard and Noller's tests⁸; ν_{\max} (KBr) 1720 (C=O), 2950 and 2885 cm⁻¹, *M*⁺, 426, C₃₀H₅₀O. This was converted to friedelan-3 β -ol by sodium borohydride reduction, which was identical with the natural product.